

Global Multidisciplinary Research

The Influence of Wadiah Current Savings, Wadiah Savings, and Bonuses on Sharia Bank Margins with Firm Size as a Moderation Variable in Islamic Banking in Indonesia Period of 2018-2023

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Abstract

The sample used in this research is sharia banks in Indonesia in 2018-2023. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling, with a total sample of 115 over 6 years. The data analysis technique used is Panel Data Regression Analysis and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) with the Eviews 12 application. The research results show a significant negative effect. Firm size is unable to moderate the influence of wadiah demand deposits on NOM (net operating margin) in sharia banking in Indonesia in the 2018-2023 period. Firm size no able to moderate the influence of wadiah savings deposits on net operating margin (NOM) in sharia banking in Indonesia for the 2018-2023 period. In future research, it is hoped that other variables will be used as moderating variables, such as dividend policy and sample companies from other sectors so that the research results can also represent other business sectors.

Keywords: Wadiah savings, wadiah current account, wadiah bonus, Net Operating Margin (NOM)

INTRODUCTION

The concept of banking is well known to the people of Indonesia and other countries in the world such as Asian, European and American countries. The first sharia bank was built in 1992, namely Bank Muamalat, as time went by other sharia banks emerged. (Shandy Utama, 2020) . Public interest in the sharia financial system is growing rapidly, marked by the emergence of financial institutions based on Islamic law, including sharia banking. Bank itself means a financial institution that collects funds and distributes them to the community. Banks have several funding sources to finance their operational activities, one of which is third party funds consisting of savings, current accounts and deposits. These third party funds are the most popular source of funds, where third party funds can be used to measure the success of a bank (Maratul Munawaroh et al., 2022)

The role of sharia banking in economic activities in Indonesia is not much different from conventional banks. The difference between the two lies in the principles of financial transactions or operations, in conventional banks one of the principles is the interest system, while in sharia banking uses the principle of profit sharing in accordance with Islamic religious law. And with the existence of Law No. 21 of 2008 concerning Sharia Banking dated 16 July 2008, the development of the sharia banking industry increasingly has an adequate legal basis and will encourage the growth of the sharia banking industry even better (N. Sari, 2015) . Islamic banks also adhere to the principles of sustainability and social responsibility. Islamic banks usually invest in the real sector which can provide economic, social and environmental benefits. According to the Financial

Services Authority, sharia banking assets are growing. This shows that people increasingly trust sharia banks to invest their money in sharia banks (Novianto, 2021)

One of the products offered by sharia banks to customers is wadiah savings and wadiah current accounts. During the wadiah contract period, it is used for wadiah savings and wadiah demand deposits. Consumers hand over control of their money to the bank based on a wadiah agreement (Nurul Hidayatul M et al., 2023) . The legal basis for this wadiah contract is of course the Koran, Ulama' fiqh agree that al-wadi'ah is a contract in the context of helping fellow human beings. The foundation is the word of Allah SWT (Lutfi, 2020) . Apart from the products offered, sharia banking also has bonuses. The existence of this bonus is a strategy for Islamic banks to attract potential customers to entrust some money to the bank. The percentage of the wawaiyah bonus is completely determined by the bank the bonus given is not mentioned at the beginning. The Wadiah concept in providing savings bonuses is taken from the bank's profits. What is meant is the profits or income of sharia banks which come from operational income from financial funds and investments (I. Sari, 2021)

The use of net margin (NOM) in banking has grown significantly in recent years. One of the factors influencing the development of the use of the NOM ratio is the increasingly tight competition in the banking industry. Increasingly fierce competition encourages banks to pay more attention to operational efficiency in order to maintain and increase profitability. Therefore, banks are increasingly using the NOM indicator as a tool to measure and monitor their operational efficiency. Apart from that, the use of the NOM ratio is also influenced by developments in technology and automation. (Budianto & Dewi, 2023)

THEORETICAL BASIS

Wadiah giro is a sharia bank fund product in the form of savings from customers in the form of giro for the security and convenience of users in their bookkeeping, contracts and sharia bank products. As long as the money is not withdrawn, the bank is allowed to use the money received from customers. It is used for financial gain to meet the bank's short-term liquidity needs. The bank owns all the profits generated from the use of the money. Banks are allowed to offer bonuses as incentives to customers as long as they are not required in advance and the amount of the bonus is not determined in advance (Nurul Hidayatul M et al., 2023)

Wadiah savings has a meaning, a savings product where clients deposit cash in LKS including banks with the aim that LKS/Sharia Bank is responsible for safeguarding the cash they have. stored or guaranteeing the arrival of cash if it is later stated that it will be returned (Maulida Jam'ah & Ahmad Amin Dalimunthe, 2022) . The practice of saving wadiah is in line with the teachings of the tabligh congregation which prioritizes sincerity and devotion in Islamic activities (Nurlaila & Liata, 2021) . Savings Wadiah savings is a type of savings that uses a wadiah contract to manage its savings. Wadiah savings deposits do not use an interest system, but instead use a profit sharing system agreed upon by both parties. In the context of Islamic finance, it is used as a form of assistance (Lanjar & Sumantri, 2022) . This is very relevant in managing tabarru' funds in sharia insurance, which are used to help participants in times of need (Fadilah & Makhrus, 2019) . The physical form and significance of savings funds in the cultural

context of the Lundayeh community is also explored (Jelinus, 2018). These various applications of savings funds highlight the diverse nature of savings funds and the importance of savings funds in the financial and cultural fields.

The Wadi'ah Bonus is a bonus given by the bank to Wadi'ah savings customers as an incentive or return in the form of money to all Wadi'ah savings customers (Rifai et al., 2024). The bonus is awarded based on factors such as the amount of funds deposited, the length of custody and the bank's financial performance. This wadiah bonus must comply with sharia principles. This wadiah bonus is an important strategy for Islamic banks.

Net Operating Margin (NOM) is a financial ratio that measures efficiency company in generating revenue from its main business operations. In the banking industry, NOM measures a bank's ability to generate operating income compared to operating costs, by calculating the ratio of net operating income to total assets. A high NOM level indicates good efficiency in generating income from business operations, but does not reflect the quality of a bank's assets or the credit risks it faces. (Budianto & Dewi, 2023)

Wadiah Current Account to Net Operating Margin (H1)

Wadiah demand deposits have a significant positive influence on net operating margin. The results of this research also show that increasing the number of wadiah demand deposits can increase the operating profit of Islamic banks, which in turn can increase the net operating margin (NOM) (Nurul Hidayatul M et al., 2023)

Wadiah Savings Against Net Operating Margin (H2)

Theoretically, Wadiah savings have a direct influence on Net Operating Margin (NOM). Because when many customers open Wadiah savings, it can increase the bank's DPK and ultimately increase the Net operating Margin (Rachman & Anggraeni, 2010).

Wadiah Bonus to Net Operating Margin (H3)

Wadiah bonuses can indirectly affect the net operating margin through several mechanisms such as increasing customer loyalty, increasing deposits and improving the bank's image (Kureishi & Hayat, 2015)

Wadiah Demand Deposits Against Net Operating Margin Moderated Firm Size(H4)

The effect of wadiah demand deposits on net operating margin which is moderated by firm size has a significant positive effect on small banks. This is because small banks generally have more limited funds and are more sensitive to changes in deposits (Kureishi & Hayat, 2015)

Wadiah Savings Against Net Operating Margin Moderated Firm Size(H5)

Wadiah savings have a significant positive influence on net operating margin when moderated by firm size. However, this also depends on several factors (Rahayu, tt, 2019)

Wadiah Bonus to Net Operating Margin Moderated Firm Size(H6)

The influence of wadiah savings on net operating margin which is moderated by

firm size shows that there is a significant positive relationship. Net operating margin is an indicator of bank profitability (dwi, 2020)

Wadiah Current Account, Wadiah Savings, and Wadiah Bonus Against Net Operating Margin (H6)

The following is the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable

RESEARCH METHODS

The type of approach uses a quantitative approach, the type of data uses secondary data. Source of data collection from ojk.co.id and related companies. The object of this research is Islamic banks in Indonesia. The research period is from 2018 to 2023. The sample in this research is Islamic banks which have complete and consistent data in 2018-2023. The data collection technique in this research is documentation, collecting data from the annual financial reports of Islamic banks. Data analysis software uses E views. The data analysis technique is multiple linear regression with the concept of a moderating variable. This technique is used to analyze the relationship between research variables statistically and to test research hypotheses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	X1	X2	X3	Y	Z
Mean	5412123	3648583	19760.50	0.536870	17.00652
Maximum	44214405	27797852	277538	2.730000	19.58000
Minimum	71477	158228	261,0000	-6.070000	15.45000
Std. dev	10888656	6544026	40830.74	1.222844	1.150836
observations	115	115	115	115	115

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on table 1, it can be seen that the number of research samples for sectors finance is a sample of 115 Financial Sector Companies listed on the Stock Exchange Indonesia (BEI) 2018-2023.

In the wadiah giro savings variable (X1) based on results Descriptive statistics

contained in Table 1 can be seen that the Wadiah current account savings variable has an average value of 5412123, a maximum value of 44214405, a value of minimum 71477, and standard deviation 10888656 and observations 115

The wadiah savings variable (X2) is based on the descriptive statistical results contained in Table 1 shows that the calculated wadiah savings variable has an average value of 3648583, a maximum value of 27797852, a minimum value of 158228, a standard deviation of 6544026 and an observation of 115

In the wadiah bonus variable (X3) based on the results of descriptive statistics contained in Table 1, it can be seen that the wadiah bonus variable has an average value of 19760.50, a maximum value of 277538, a value of minimum 2,610,000, standard deviation 40830.74, and observations 115

In the Net Operating Margin (NOM) (Y) variable, based on the results of descriptive statistics in Table 1, it can be seen that the Net Operating Margin (NOM) variable has an average value of 0.536870, a maximum value of 2.730000, a value of minimum -6.070000, and standard deviation 1.222844 and observations 115

The variable (Z) is based on the results of descriptive statistics contained in Table 1 shows that the firm size variable has an average value of 1,700,652, a maximum value of 1,958,000, a minimum 1,545,000, standard deviation 1,150,835, and observations 115

Selection of Panel Data Regression Models

selecting a panel data regression model to determine the best method between Common Effect, Fixed Effect or Random Effect

Test chow

Table 2. Chow Test Results

Effects Test	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	12.276058	(4,107)	0.0000
Chi-square cross-section	43.434937	4	0.0000

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on the table above, the results of the Chow test show that the chisquare cross-section probability value is 0.0000 <0.05. So it can be said that in this test, the model is the best to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM)

Hausman test

Table 3. Hausman Test Results

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistics	Chi-Sq. df	Prob.
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Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Random cross-section	48.561655	3	0.0000
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From the table above, it can be seen that the Hausman test results show a value probability of 0.0000 < 0.05. So it can be said that in this test, the model The best one to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM)

Classical Assumptions
Normality Test

Table 4. Normality Test Results

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on the picture above, it shows that the probability value is 0.000000, which means the probability value is above 0.05 ($0.145120 > 0.05$). So it can be concluded that the data in this study is not normally distributed.

Multicollinearity test

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test Results

	LOG(X1)	X2	X3
LOG(X1)	1	0.751205	0.391260
X2	0.751205	1	0.31080
X3	0.391260	0.310680	1

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on table 5, the results of the multicollinearity test can be seen if the correlation value between variables independent values are all < 0.85 . This means that research data is not available multicollinearity between independent variables

Heteroscedasticity test

Table 6. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	0.754378	0.129366	5.831339	0.0000
X1	2.01E-10	3.37E-08	0.005981	0.9952
X2	-2.54E-09	4.73E-08	-0.053741	0.9572
X3	8.68E-07	3.44E-06	0.252673	0.8010

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on the table above, the results of the heteroscedasticity test show that the probability value is The result is above 0.05. A regression model is said to be free from heteroscedasticity. if it has a probability value above 0.05. So it can be concluded that in the regression model used in this research, heteroscedasticity does not occur.

PANEL DATA REGRESSION ANALYSIS

The following is a panel data regression using the best method, namely fixed effect model (FEM) regression.

Fixed effect model (FEM) panel data regression analysis

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	0.170199	0.165476	1.028540	0.3060
X1	2.90E-08	4.30E-08	0.674276	0.5016
X2	6.24E-08	6.05E-08	1.032844	0.3040
X3	-9.22E-07	4.40E-06	-0.209772	0.8342

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Moderation regression analysis

Moderating variables can be interpreted as variables that can strengthen or weaken the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The following are the test results from the moderation regression analysis

Table 8. Results of moderation regression analysis

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	-11.28139	12.01271	-0.939122	0.3499
X1	-7.34E-07	1.67E-06	-0.440651	0.6604
X2	1.58E-06	1.46E-06	1.081226	0.2821
X3	6.26E-06	9.79E-05	0.063903	0.9492
Z	0.686468	0.726359	0.945080	0.3468
X1_Z	-8.24E-08	7.85E-08	-1.050683	0.2959
X2_Z	3.94E-08	8.39E-08	0.469804	0.6395
X3_Z	-5.67E-07	5.39E-06	-0.105305	0.9163

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Statistical Test

T test

Table 9. T Test Results

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	0.063977	0.439322	0.145626	0.8845
X1	-3.52E-07	1.62E-06	-0.217883	0.8279
X1_Z	-9.40E-08	7.75E-08	-1.213954	0.2275
X2	1.82E-06	1.44E-06	1.263138	0.2094
X2_Z	2.18E-08	8.18E-08	0.266955	0.7900
X3	-7.93E-06	9.67E-05	-0.082034	0.9348
X3_Z	1.64E-07	5.33E-06	0.030870	0.9754

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on the t test (partial) that the author has carried out in this research, it can be seen that The results obtained from the t test are as follows:

1) Hypothesis 1 (H1): Wadiah current account savings have no effect on NOM. From the test results on variable 2018-2023.

2) Hypothesis 2 (H2): Wadiah savings have an effect on NOM. From the test results on variable X2, the probability value is $0.2094 < 0.5$. This shows that wadiah savings deposits have a significant effect on NOM in some sharia banking companies in Indonesia during this period 2018-2023.

3) Hypothesis 3 (H3): Wadiah Bonus has no effect on NOM. From the test results on variable X3, a probability value of $0.9348 > 0.5$. This shows that wadiah bonuses have no effect on NOM in some sharia banking companies in Indonesia during this period 2018-2023.

4) Hypothesis 4 (H4): Wadiah Current Account Savings has a moderated effect on NOM Firm Size. From the test results on variables X1*Z, the probability value is $0.2275 < 0.5$. This shows that Firm Size is able to moderate the influence of wadiah demand deposits on NOM in some sharia banking companies in Indonesia for the 2018-2023 period.

5) Hypothesis 5 (H5): Wadiah Savings Savings has no moderated effect on NOM Firm Size. From the test results on the variable X2*Z, the probability value is $0.7900 > 0.5$. This shows that Firm Size is not able to moderate the influence of wadiah demand deposits on NOM in some sharia banking companies in Indonesia for the 2018-2023 period.

6) Hypothesis 6 (H6): Wadiah Bonus has no moderated effect on NOM Firm Size. From the test results on the variable X_3^*Z , the probability value is $0.9754 > 0.5$. This shows that Firm Size unable to moderate the influence of wadiah bonuses on NOM in some sharia banking companies in Indonesia for the 2018-2023 period.

F test

Table 10. F Test Results

Prob (F statistic)	0.000000
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Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

The F test in this study uses a significance value of 0.05 or 5% with the if criterion The significance value of $F < 0.05$ means the regression coefficient is suitable to be used. The results of the F test in the table above show a significance value of F of 0.000000, this value is smaller than the value The significance is 0.05. And the calculated F value is $9,002,032 > F$ table. So, it can be concluded that wadiah checking deposits, wadiah savings deposits and wadiah bonuses simultaneously have an influence on the net operating margin.

Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 11. Coefficient of determination test results

Adjusted R-Squared	0.412433
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Source: Eviews (Data processed by

Coefficient of Determination, used to show how much the variable contributes independent in the regression model in explaining variations in the dependent variable. Based on the table above, the results of the panel data regression test on NOM as a variable dependent, shows that the Adjusted R2 value is 0.412433.

DISCUSSION

The effect of wadiah giro savings on NOM's net operating margin

Based on the test results table, it shows that the probability value of wadiah demand deposits is 0.8279, which means it is greater than 0.05. This shows that wadiah demand deposits have no effect on NOM in some sharia banking companies in Indonesia for the period 2018-2023. So the hypothesis is rejected. The test results also show a negative direction with the coefficient and t statistic values. In previous research, Wadiah current account savings did not have a significant influence on net operating margin. However, research conducted by Elga Puji Rahayu shows that Wadiah demand deposits have a positive effect on net operating margin. This may be because wadiah demand deposits are used as a source of funds to increase bank operational activities. However, keep in mind that this influence can vary depending on banking conditions.

The effect of Wadiah savings on net operating margin

Based on table 9, it shows that the probability of wadiah savings is 0.2821, which means it is greater than the significant value of 0.005. This shows that wadiah savings deposits have no effect on the net operating margin in sharia banking in Indonesia. And in previous research it was stated that wadiah savings deposits did not have a significant effect, this was due to several factors such as the level of credit risk, macroeconomic

conditions and bank management strategies. So the second hypothesis: Wadiah savings have an effect on the net operating margin is not accepted.

The effect of wadiah bonuses on net operating margin (NOM)

Based on the test results, the probability value of the wadiah bonus is greater than 0.05, namely 0.9348. The results of this test show that wadiah bonuses do not have a significant effect on the net operating margin in Islamic banking in Indonesia. In previous research, wadiah bonuses can affect net operating margin by increasing or reducing bank operational costs. Hypothesis 3: wadiah bonuses have an effect on net operating margin is rejected.

The effect of wadiah demand deposits on net operating margin is moderated by firm size

Based on the results of the T test that has been carried out, it was found that the probability value is 0.2275, which means it is greater than 0.05. This shows that firm size is unable to moderate the influence of wadiah current account savings on net operating margin. H4: Wadiah demand deposits have an effect on net operating margin, moderated by firm size, rejected.

The effect of Wadiah savings on net operating margin is moderated by firm size

It can be seen from the T test results that the probability value is 0.7900 which is greater than 0.05. This shows that firm size cannot moderate the influence of Wadiah Savings savings on net operating margin. Previous research explains that research on Wadiah savings deposits on net operating margin moderated by firm size produces different results, depending on the bank object studied. So hypothesis 5 is rejected

The effect of wadiah bonuses on net operating margin is moderated by firm size

The T test results show that the probability value is 0.9754, where this value is greater than 0.05. This shows that firm size is unable to moderate the influence of wadiah bonuses on net operating margin. This is caused by several factors as explained in previous research, namely capital structure factors, market access and risk management strategies. So the 6th hypothesis is rejected

The effect of wadiah demand deposits, wadiah savings, wadiah bonuses on net operating margin

In the research results, the f test obtained a result of 0.00000, this is smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the wadiah bonus Wadiah savings and wadiah current accounts have an effect on the net operating margin. Then h7 is accepted.

However, keep in mind that each study is likely to get different results, depending on the existing factors.

CONCLUSION

The results of the research show that together, wadiah checking deposits, wadiah savings and wadiah bonuses have an effect on NOM. This means that the combination of these three variables has an effect on the profitability of Islamic banking. However, individually, these three variables does not have a significant effect on NOM. This means that an increase in just one variable, without being accompanied by an increase in other

variables, will not produce a significant effect on NOM.

Bank size (firm size) also cannot moderate the influence of these three variables on NOM. This means that the size of the bank does not affect how wadiah checking deposits, wadiah savings and wadiah bonuses affect NOM. These findings provide several important implications for Islamic banking. First, Islamic banks need to consider various other factors, apart from wadiah demand deposits, wadiah savings, and wadiah bonuses, to increase NOM. These other factors may include productive financing distribution, operational efficiency, and the development of innovative products and services.

Second, Islamic banks need to implement a comprehensive strategy to increase wadiah demand deposits, wadiah savings and wadiah bonuses. This can be done by offering products and services that are attractive to customers, providing education about Wadiah products, and improving the quality of customer service. Islamic banks need to continue to monitor economic developments and regulations related to Islamic banking. This is important to ensure that the strategies implemented remain relevant and effective in increasing NOM.

This research has several limitations. First, the data used only comes from sharia banking in Indonesia for the 2018-2023 period. Therefore, the results of this study may not be generalizable to Islamic banking in other countries or other time periods.

Second, this research only uses multiple linear regression methods. Other methods, such as more complex econometric models, may provide more accurate results.

Further research with different research objects and periods, as well as using more complex methods, may be needed to obtain more generalizable results and provide a more comprehensive picture of the influence of savings and wadiah bonuses on Islamic banking NOM.

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